

Sample Name: PA UV 1-5 μm

Material: Polyamide (Nylon-6,6)

Size: 1-5 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Structure

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 50% particles are <1 μm
- Median diameter (D_{50v}) = 4,52 μm
- Particles have a rounded, irregular morphology
- 2.0×10^{11} particles per gram
- 15938 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$ (PA) determined by XRF
- No changes due to milling or aging observed in FTIR spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PA spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
5,19	3,30	1,95	1,28	0,93	4,52	$2,0 \times 10^{11}$	15938

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$	99,937
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	74
S	11
Cl	2040
K	19
Ca	29
Ti	2
Cr	23
Mn	1
Fe	86
Ni	7
Cu	2
Zn	2
Mo	1

Chemical Bonding (Using $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ provided by TNO)

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

